

ABSTRACT

A Patent Act offers an assurance of a property through a sovereign authority to an inventor. The Guarantee is furnished on an invention, Product, or Process. There are 162 Sections within the Indian Patent Act 1970 with 23 chapters.

On the premise of Research, current Statistics file From the USPTO, approx 52% of all Patent Filled are approved. Guruswamy Nataraj turned into the primary patent Agent in India. A civil Engineer, George Alfred De Penning of 7, Grant's Lane, Calcutta on 3rd Mar 1856 offers India's first Patent for his Invention -An Efficient Punkah Pulling Machine.

Filing of patents has increased from 42763 in 2014-15 to 66440 in 2021-22, an extra 50% boom in the past few years. There are 4 Patent Offices in India, which might be placed in Kolkata (Main Office), Mumbai, Chennai, and Delhi.

This article covers the True means of Patent with a proper definition and meaning. Relation with IPR in connection with distinction among Copyright Trademark and Patent. A specified Study of Origin of Patent. Also, it covers all sorts of patents in India. Every coin has two facets so; right here we've mentioned the pros and cons of the Patent Act in addition to drawbacks. The main body contains why Protection of Invention is necessary. What can happen if you don't patent your invention as well as how Patent can Increase new Inventions?

INTRODUCTION

A patent is nothing but a Right Guarantee to an invention, Product, or Process, in reality, a brand new manner of doing something or to present a brand new Technical approach to a problem. The phrase patent is derived from the Latin phrase *pater*, which precisely approaches "to put open". A patent is not anything, however, a report issued through authorities to the inventor which offers permission to solely manufacture, make use of and promote on disclosure of the discovery for an exact length of time. Unlike patents, a monopoly existed in which Inventions have been now no longer disclosed and solely sold. Indian Patent Law is described as patent rights granted for innovations protecting a brand new and creative Process, a product, or an editorial of manufacture which might be capable of fulfilling the patent Eligibility necessities of getting novelty, able to commercial utility, and creative steps.

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPR)

It is a class that incorporates intangible creations of the human mind under assets. There are many sorts of highbrow assets; the typically recognized sorts are COPYRIGHTS, PATENTS, and TRADEMARKS. The idea of that evolved in England during the 17th and 18th centuries. "Intellectual assets" States for use within the 19 century. The foremost reason for highbrow asset regulation is to inspire the Creative type of highbrow goods. This lets people defend their thoughts and save you copying. Patents, Copyright, and trademark are exclusive sorts of highbrow assets.

- **What is a Copyright?**

It is a set of rights for an authentic painting given to you. These rights consist of the proper breeding of paintings, putting together by-product works, distributing copies, carrying out the paintings publicly, and showing the paintings publicly. As the copyright owner, you've got the authority to maintain the paintings, to switch them personally to at least one or extra people, or to switch them together to at least one or extra people. You can professionalize your paintings via licensing, assigning, and different varieties of transfers.

- **What is a Patent?**

The foremost goal of the patent regulation is to inspire innovation and commercialization of improvement Progress. A patent protects innovations. Patent regulation stimulates inventors to publicly divulge their innovations in alternate for positive different rights. Inventions consist of new and beneficial tactics for manufacturers, machines, and compositions depending in addition to enhancements to those with copyright safety, to get patent safety one should first practice for and be granted a patent from the U.S. Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO). Unlike the copyright registration technique, the patent utility technique is expensive, complex, difficult, and time-consuming and commonly needs to now no longer be tried without the help of a skilled patent legal professional or agent.

- **What is a Trademark?**

A trademark is not anything, however, a phrase, symbol, and/or a layout that identifies and distinguishes the supply of the products of 1 birthday celebration from the ones of others. A provider mark is a phrase,

symbol, and/or layout that identifies and distinguishes the supply of a provider in preference to goods. For instance, emblem names, slogans, and logos. Similar to copyright, someone now no longer signs up for an indicator or provider mark to acquire safety rights, however, there are positive criminal advantages to registering the mark with the USPTO.

THE DIFFERENCE

POINTS	COPYRIGHT	PATENT	TRADEMARK
PROTECTION	Original works (authorship), such as books, articles, songs, photographs, choreography, sound recordings, and other works	Inventions, for example, processes, machines, manufacturers, compositions of matter as well as improvements to the same	Any word, phrase, symbol, or design that identifies and distinguishes the source of the goods of one party from those of others
BASIC REQUIREMENTS FOR PROTECTION	Work should be original, creative and, fixed in a tangible medium	An invention must be new, useful, and ambiguous.	A mark must be in particular, it must be capable of identifying the source of a particular good
TIME PERIOD	70 years after the death of the author	Death of author 20 years	As long as the mark is used. Death of author 20 years

RIGHTS GUARANTEED	Right to control the reproduction, making of derivative work distribution and public performance and display of the copyrighted works	Right to prevent others from making, selling, using, or importing the patented invention	Right to use the mark and to prevent others from using similar marks in a way that would cause likelihood-of-confusion about the origin of goods or services.

ORIGIN OF THE PATENT ACT

In the 1300s, the individual that based assets inside the Alps recited assets rights for mining, wood, and water. As the opposition progressed, privileges were granted for beneficial creation. In 1409, the first patent was granted to a German for the development of the version mill. The first English patent was granted for a length of 20 12 months to John of Utynam on making stained glass. For the time being, the French superior the device through Registration and examination. In the United States, a Patent turned into granted for a grain elevator 'hopper boy' To Oliver Evans.

INDIAN SCENARIO

The records of Patent regulation in India began to evolve in 1911 when the Indian Patents and Designs Act, 1911 was approved. The Patents Act, of 1970 is the regulation that to date governs patents in India. It first came under pressure

in 1972 The Office of the Controller General of Patents, Designs and Trademarks or CGPDTM is framed liable for the Indian patent act. The workplace of the CGPDTM is primarily based totally in Mumbai. The Patent Office has its nerve center in Calcutta and has branches in New Delhi, Chennai and Mumbai. Nagpur hosts the workplace of the Patent Information System and additionally the National Institute for Intellectual Property Management. This Act remained under pressure for approximately 30 years with no amendments, however, in the year 1883, positive changes within the patent regulation have been made in the United Kingdom and it was taken into consideration that the one changes need to additionally be included in the Indian Law. In 1888, an Act turned added to consolidate and amend the regulation regarding Invention and designs in conformity with the amendments made within the U.K. regulation The Indian Patents and Designs Act, 1911, (Act II of 1911) changed all of the preceding Acts. This Act delivered patent management below the control of the Controller of Patents for the primary time. This Act was similarly amended in 1920 to go into Reciprocal preparations with the UK and different international locations for securing priority. In 1930, further amendments were made to incorporate, inter-alia, provisions regarding the supply of mystery patents, the patent of addition, use of invention through Government, powers of the Controller to rectify the sign up of patent, and growth of time of the patent from 14 Years to sixteen years. In 1945, a change was made to offer for submitting a provisional specification and submission of the entire specification within 9 Months. After Independence, it was felt that the Indian Patents & Designs Act, 1911 turned into no longer fulfilled its objective. It turned into a determined ideal to enact complete patent regulation Owing to giant modifications in political and monetary situations within the United States. Accordingly, the Government of India constituted a committee below the Chairmanship of Justice (Dr.) Bakshi Tekchand, a retired Judge of Lahore High Court, In 1949

checked the patent regulation in India with the purpose to make certain that the patent system is conducive to the country-wide interest.

TYPES OF PATENT OPERATIONS GRANTED IN INDIA

- Divisional Application is a document in which the aspirant wishes to divide an operation to grant or similar operations if a selected operation claims to be similar to one invention.
- A conference operation is filed for claiming a Priority date grounded at the identical or extensively analogous operation filed in any of the conference international locations.
- It's a transnational operation to streamline patent operation techniques in several international locations at one go. It's Governed through the Patent Cooperation Treaty. It may be verified in over 142 Countries.
- A public segment operation is filed in each of the United States in which safety is sought. The public segment operation should be filed within 30 or 31 months from the priority date or the International shape date, whichever is earlier.
- An Ordinary or Non-Provisional operation is filed if the aspirant doesn't have any priority to Claim or in a case in which the operation isn't always filed in the overall performance of the preceding conference operation. The non-provisional operation, while filed, Must be supported through an entire specification depicting the discovery in detail.
- In the patent of addition, the aspirant can document a patent of addition, if there may be a revision of the discovery which has previously been carried out for or patented. A patent of addition can most effectively be granted after the entitlement of the determined patent; hence, no

separate renewal determination is to be remitted for the duration of the time of the principle Patent.

WHAT IS THE MAIN PURPOSE OF A PATENT?

A patent is the granting of assets proper through a sovereign authority to an Inventor. A patent presents the inventor with different rights to the patented Process, layout, or invention for a positive length in an alternative to complete disclosure of the discovery.

BASIC ADVANTAGES OF THE PATENT

It converts your Idea or Invention into a transactional outcome. Like you may earn, you may make cash via your Invention. Just like property and commercial enterprises you may promote your specific concept and Convert Invention Monetary Fund. After patenting your invention you may freely proportion your concept to anyone.

CRITERIA FOR PATENT TO BE GRANTED

According to Section 2(1) (j) of the Indian Patent Act, "invention" is a brand new Product or technique related to a creative step and able to commercial Application. Further, Section 2(1) of the Act defines 'new invention' as any Invention or generation which has now no longer been expected through the booklet in Any report or used within the united states or some other place within the international earlier than the Date of submitting of patent utility with an entire specification, i.e., the Subject depend has now no longer fallen in a public area or that it does now no longer shape component Of the kingdom of art. An

Inventive Step: According to Section 2(1) (a) "creative step" approach is a feature of an invention that includes technical improvements compared to the Existing expertise or has monetary importance or that makes the discovery now no longer appears to someone professional within the art. Industrial Application: The 1/3 criterion of patentability is that the Invention needs to be commercially utilized. Section 2(1)(a)(c) of The Patents Act, 1970, defines "Capable of Industrial utility" concerning an invention because the invention is "able to be made or used In an industry." Therefore, to be patentable, an invention should be beneficial.

BASIS FOR REJECTION OF PATENT IN INDIA

Rejections by the IPO have been raised mostly in section 15 proceedings, which accounts for 1637 rejections. Section 15 is not quoted in isolation and is often used in conjunction with other sections, at times, the IPO calls for a hearing (under section 14), requesting the applicant for clarification. In cases where the applicant fails to clarify the objections raised under Section 14, the Controller rejects the application under section 15.

In 54 Cases, the Controller rejected the operation solely grounded on section 16, i.e. the operation didn't qualify as a divisional operation under the Act. Section 16 was quoted along with other sections in 117 Cases.

WHEN INDIA REALIZED further ABOUT INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

An Issue of Turmeric Patent 10, 11

Turmeric grease paint is extensively used in India as Medicine, colour, and food component. The US granted a patent on turmeric To the University of Mississippi Medical Centre, in 1995 for crack mending property. A right has been granted to disturb and vend. After 2 times, India's Council of Scientific and Industrial Research challenged the university based on the novelty of the discovery. The USPTO cancelled the patent due to a Lack of novelty.

An Issue of Basmati Rice Patent 12

Basmati rice is a notorious cereal in India and is notorious for its smell and taste. This rice is grown in the Basmati region of India performing in its ambrosial taste. Over hundreds of times, this rice was developed by an Indian planter, but a Texan Company obtained a patent for a cross strain with American long-grain rice. The US granted a patent to the company based on an aroma, the extension of the Grain on cuisine, and chalkiness and since also the Company can charge the growers to grow rice and Not allow planting the seeds for the ensuing time's Crop. So India filed a solicitation with scientific substantiation, saying that the utmost kinds of Basmati retain these rates. The USPTO accepted the solicitation.

THE PATENTS ACT, DT.20-5-2003 W.E.F. 16

To cross the walls of passages other than EMR, India introduced an alternate correction bill and several changes were made to the Act. The following are the

crucial changes made. Patentable Inventions, Section 2 of the Patents Act, 1970, define an invention as a new product or process involving an inventive step and ability of artificial operation. With the offer of the preface of product patents, the description is broadened by the preface of the words 'non-obvious ' and ' useful ' synonymous with inventive steps and the ability of artificial operation, independently.

DOWNSIDES IN PATENTS ACT, 1970

Indians have the station of sharing knowledge with others without guarding it, which is in turn, a major Drawback. There are no Beings in the Patents Act, 1970 for the protection of the ancient knowledge which is being used for generations. There are some introductory disadvantages as well like Patenting commodity is a precious Process that it's only for a limited time.

THE CONCLUSION

The Patent Act simply protects your brand new idea by simply protecting your patent rights. This will stop others from duplicating your original product. The Patent Act provides you the right to take action against making a duplicate copy of your innovation and, of course, selling your invention without your permission. But where this term came from, came from German in the year 1300. This act came to India in 1911 and got its actual place and recognition in 1970, after Independence. Under IPR, we have copyright, trademarks, patents, and so on. Every right has its importance; the Patent protects your Invention and allows you to sell your invention, to convert your Idea into Money. A patent encourages a person to make more inventions as they feel secure and can take action at any time on anyone who copies their invention.

But what comes, in the end, is what if you don't patent your innovation? Anyone can still use your idea, and you won't be able to take any legal action. According to general psychology, we always end up discussing our ideas with others. They may copy your invention and sell your product and earn money without your permission. In short, a patent protects your invention. So the only solution to protect your invention is the timely registration of your patent and understanding of its perks.

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